

**THE STATUS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE
INTERNATIONAL HANDBOOK OF UNIVERSITIES OF WORLD HIGHER
EDUCATION DATABASE (WHED)****Mohamed Rifky¹, Kasun Kumara Dissanayake², SMBM Arshad³, Murodjon Samadiy⁴**^{1,3}Eastern University, Sri Lanka.²Tashkent Chemical Technological Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.³Lincoln University College, Malaysia.⁴Qarshi Institute of Economics and Pedagogy, Qarshi, Uzbekistan<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10139583>

Abstract. *This article represents the current status of accreditation of higher education institutions of Uzbekistan in the International Association of Universities (IAU), which is a membership-based organization that provides publications & portals, peer-to-peer learning, research, expertise & trends analysis, advisory services, and publishing to the global higher education community. The IAU is the only worldwide university association that is inclusive and has minimal membership barriers; nonetheless, despite its numerous advantages, only few percentages of institutions are members. The rating of world universities is a crucial component in considering them as a recognized higher education service provider.*

The ministry of higher education, science and innovation has introduced measures to improve the standard of higher education to compete globally with international standard. The IAU, a world higher education database, has identified 64 Uzbekistan universities and institutions as recognized higher education organizations in these metrics. However, the number of university branches that may participate in world rankings is severely limited owing to limitations in the procedure for registering them in the world ranking.

Keywords: *institutes; universities; IAU; WHED*

Introduction

World ranking of higher education institutions has been a trend and blooming sector in higher education and they identified the important of this process during the last three decades [1]. The relevance of internationalization is being recognized as it emerges as a popular strategy for advancing higher education.

It now plays a significant part in the national economic development, the national education system, and initiatives that promote cultural diversity. The aim of this research is to highlight the current state of these phenomena, their brief historical background, and the justifications for internationalizing higher education. Looking at contemporary trends in networking, distinctiveness, and internationalization in higher education, we propose that colleges in need of more legitimacy and "birth" in the age of globalization are more inclined to join inclusive international networks like the IAU [3].

As a result, we anticipate that lower-status and younger colleges will be more inclined to participate. To examine the assumptions behind these arguments, we employ regression models. Even after adjusting for other variables, our findings are consistent with these assumptions.

IAU is largely supported by membership fees and relies on them to effectively carry out its diverse portfolio of activities, which includes a series of online webinars and topical discussions, events and conferences, publications, projects, and other initiatives [4]. We're curious why some institutions are keener to get membership in the IAU, and universities with a greater statutory

requirement are likely to obtain this certification due to the growing demand of higher education. This viewpoint, which is important in organizational studies, is based on two reasons from modern organizational theory [5].

In the framework of higher education reforms, this article explains the status of the internationalization of Uzbekistani higher education system. Using data from the World Higher Education Database, it focuses on how globalization has affected Uzbekistan's higher education system.

Discussions

In Uzbekistan, a new movement has emerged to have higher education organizations compete with foreign organizations. Uzbekistan is presently taking steps to improve the rankings of universities and institutions in order to internationalize them. The management and administration of universities have seen substantial changes across the world. Universities have likewise evolved from "specialized bodies" of public sector and should show their legitimacy as part of this process while under pressure to become more independent, accountable, better, relevant, and worldwide. Policymakers' rhetoric at the national governance level has evolved from an emphasis on national development to one on global competitiveness [6].

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- Centro de Estudio y Diagnóstico de las Dignacias del Uruguay – Uruguayan University Institute for the Study and Diagnosis of Malocclusions (IUCEDDU)
16. YMCA University Institute (Instituto Universitario Asociación Cristiana de Jóvenes (IUACJ))
- **Uzbekistan**
1. Andijan Agricultural Institute Andijon Qishloq Xo' Jalik Instituti
 2. Andijan Institute of Engineering Andijon Mashinasozlik Instituti
 3. Andijan State Medical Institute Andijon Davlat Tibbiyot Instituti – Andijanskij Meditsinskij Institut (ASMI)
 4. Andijan State University Andijon Davlat Universiteti (ASU)
 5. Bukhara High-Technology Engineering Institute Buxoro Yuqori Texnologiyalar Muxandislik-Texnika Instituti (BTIFLI)
 6. Bukhara State Medical Institute Buxoro Davlat Tibbiyot Instituti
 7. Bukhara State University Buxoro Davlat Universiteti (BSU)
 8. Fergana Polytechnic Institute Farg'ona Politehnika Instituti (FPI)
 9. Fergana State University Farg'ona Davlat Universiteti (FSU)
 10. Gulistan State University Guliston Davlat Universiteti (GSU)
 11. Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute Jizzax Politehnika Instituti (JPTI)
 12. Jizzax State Pedagogical Institute Jizzax Davlat Pedagogika Instituti – A. Qodiriy Nomidagi Jizzax Davlat Pedagogika Instituti
 13. Karakalpak State University Qoraqalpoq Davlat Universiteti – Berdaq nomidagi Qoraqalpoq Davlat Universiteti
 14. Kokand State Pedagogical Institute Qo'qon Davlat Pedagogika Instituti
 15. Management Development Institute of Singapore in Tashkent Toshkent Shahridagi Singapur Menejmentni Rivojlantirish Instituti (MDIS Tashkent)
 16. Namangan Institute of Engineering and Technology Namangan Muhandislik- Texnologiya Instituti
 17. Namangan Pedagogical-Engineering Institute Namangan Muhandislik-Pedagogika Instituti
 18. Namangan State University Namangan Davlat Universiteti – Namanganskij Gosudartsevnij Universitet (NamSU)
 19. National Institute of Arts and Design Milliy Rassomchilik va Dizayn Instituti – Kamoliddin Behzod Nomidagi Milliy Rassomlik va Dizayn Instituti
 20. National University of Uzbekistan O'zbekiston Milliy Universiteti – Mirzo Ulug'bek Nomidagi O'zbekiston Milliy Universiteti
 21. Navoiy State Mining Institute Navoiy Davlat Konchilik Instituti (NSMI)
 22. Navoiy State Pedagogical Institute Navoiy Davlat Pedagogika Instituti
 23. Nukus State Pedagogical Institute Nukus Davlat Pedagogika Instituti
 24. Qarshi Engineering – Economic Institute Qarshi Muhandislik Iqtisodiyot Instituti (KEEI)
 25. Qarshi State University Qarshi Davlat Universiteti
 26. Samarkand Agricultural Institute Samarqand Qishloq xo' Jalik Instituti
 27. Samarkand Institute of Economy and Service Samarqand Iqtisodiyot va Servis Instituti (SCI)
 28. Samarkand State Architecture Institute Samarqand Davlat Arxitektura-qurilish Instituti (SSACI)
 29. Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages Samarqand Davlat Chet Tillar Instituti (SamSIFL)
 30. Samarkand State Medical Institute Samarqand Davlat Tibbiyot Instituti (SSMI)
 31. Samarkand State University Samarqand Davlat Universiteti – Alisher Navoiy nomidagi Samarqand Davlat Universiteti (SSU)
 32. State Conservatory of Uzbekistan O'zbekiston Davlat Konservatoriyasi
 33. Tashkent Automobile and Road Construction Institute Toshkent Avtomobil-Yo'llar Instituti – Toshkent Avtomobil – Yo'llar Instituti (TARCI)
 34. Tashkent Branch of Moscow State University named after M. Lomonosov M. Lomonosov Nomidagi Moskva Davlat Universitetining Toshkent Shahridagi Filiali
 35. Tashkent Branch of the Russian State University of Oil and Gas named after I. Gubkin I. Gubkin Nomidagi Rossiya davlat Neft va Gaz Universitetining Toshkent Shahridagi Filiali
 36. Tashkent Branch of the Russian University of Economics named after G. Plekhanov G. Plekhanov Nomidagi Rossiya Iqtisodiyot Akademiyasining Toshkent Shahar Filiali
 37. Tashkent Chemical-Technological Institute Toshkent Kimyo-Texnologiya Instituti (TICT)
 38. Tashkent Institute of Architecture and Construction Toshkent Arxitektura-Qurilish Instituti (TASI)

Figure: 1 some of the Uzbekistan universities and institutes recognized by the IAU in 2021

Members have preferential access to a wide range of services, but they are also available to other Higher Education stakeholders such as organizations, institutions, higher education authorities, policy and decision-makers, experts, administrators, instructors, researchers, and students [7].

As a worldwide platform for leaders of institutions and groups, the IAU brings together and links almost 130 countries to identify, reflect on, and act on shared goals. It serves as the

worldwide and global voice of higher education sector to a diversification of international and intergovernmental bodies, most notably UNESCO [7]. Out of this 64 institutes and universities have registered as a member of this database which is shown in figure 1.

There are several branches of major universities available throughout the Uzbekistan, and the branches were not allowed to rank in the international data base despite having separate legal entities, which is one of the major constraints encountered in the process of obtaining certification and world ranking in Uzbekistan.

Conclusion

The greatest way to recruit international students to study in Uzbekistan is for them to earn worldwide rankings and be listed in the international the handbook of universities published by the World Higher Education Database. At the moment, 64 higher education organizations, including universities and institutes, have registered and received membership from Uzbekistan, and this number will grow in order to attract more international students. Due to database restrictions, university branches are having significant difficulty registering for membership.

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